

How to Acknowledge the ARDC in a Co-Investment Partnership Project

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Related Documents	ARDC Acknowledgement Guidelines Persistent Identifiers for ARDC Investments policy How to Acknowledge Use of ARDC Services and Co-Investment Project Outputs and Services
Purpose	<p>This guideline is for users of ARDC services and ARDC partners.</p> <p>It outlines how ARDC partners can acknowledge ARDC project co-investment</p>

For ARDC Project Partners: How to Acknowledge the ARDC in a Co-Investment Partnership Project

In line with the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) acknowledgement guidelines, all partners in ARDC co-investment projects are required to acknowledge the ARDC co-investment and support using standard text, together with ARDC and NCRIS logos.

The acknowledgement is required on project websites and webpages, as well as in all marketing and communication materials, including presentations, articles, media releases, posters and brochures.

An ARDC Investment Identifier - a ([CrossRef Grant ID](#)) DOI - is required to publicly identify the ARDC's co-investment in a project. This identifier is issued by the ARDC, and the project team will be advised of the DOI as per the [Persistent Identifiers for ARDC Investments](#) policy and procedures.

The standard text is as follows:

Co-investment through the ARDC Thematic Research Data Commons initiatives:

- [Project name] is a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) through the [Planet/People/HASS and Indigenous] Research Data Commons (DOI: [insert project DOI hyperlinked to DOI URL]). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).
 - Example of DOI and DOI link: 'DOI: [10.47486/DP728](https://doi.org/10.47486/DP728)' hyperlinked with the URL: <https://doi.org/10.47486/DP728>

Co-investment through other ARDC initiatives:

- [Project name] is a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) (DOI: [insert project DOI hyperlinked to DOI URL]). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).
 - Example of DOI and DOI link: 'DOI: [10.47486/DP728](https://doi.org/10.47486/DP728)' hyperlinked with the URL: <https://doi.org/10.47486/DP728>

Acknowledging services supported through a co-investment partnership:

- [Service name] is supported through a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [through the Planet/People/HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons] (DOI: [insert project DOI hyperlinked to DOI URL]). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).
 - Example of DOI and DOI link: 'DOI: [10.47486/DP728](https://doi.org/10.47486/DP728)' hyperlinked with the URL: <https://doi.org/10.47486/DP728>

Examples

Co-investment project through the ARDC Thematic Research Data Commons example:

Enhancing Discoverability and Impact: Standardising National Environmental Science Program (NESP) Marine and Coastal Data with Persistent Identifiers is a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) through the Planet Research Data Commons (DOI: [10.3565/pkjc-z984](https://doi.org/10.3565/pkjc-z984)). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Co-investment project through other ARDC initiatives example:

Spark: A Fire Behaviour Modelling Platform was a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) (DOI: [10.47486/DC004](https://doi.org/10.47486/DC004)). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Acknowledging services supported through a co-investment partnership example:

Open Ecoacoustics is supported through a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) through the Planet Research Data Commons (DOI: [10.3565/ts8c-ee10](https://doi.org/10.3565/ts8c-ee10)). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Using the ARDC and NCRIS logos

Wherever possible, please use the standard text above together with the ARDC and NCRIS logos on websites and presentations about the co-investment project.

Please use both the logos for posters, brochures and other marketing materials, mention the ARDC and NCRIS in press releases, and tag the ARDC in social media posts.

Logos and guidance are available to download in the ARDC brand assets for partners.

Available logos include:

- ARDC logo (eps and png formats)
- NCRIS logo, or Australian Government and NCRIS logo lockup (eps and png formats)

Logo variations, including reverse and monochromatic, are available upon request.

For assistance, and approval of the use of the ARDC and NCRIS logos and acknowledgement text, contact ARDC Marketing and Communication team at comms@ardc.edu.au.

In your email, please include a screenshot or link to your website, publication or project showing the logos and acknowledgement. If it's related to a publication, we'll be pleased to share the publication with our networks.

Download the ARDC's brand asset pack for partners:

- [ARDC brand asset pack for partners](#)

A Communication Toolkit for ARDC Co-investment Projects

A Communication toolkit is available to help ARDC co-investment project teams develop a communication strategy to be applied throughout the project's lifecycle - from its establishment to building and launching phases.

Your communication strategy will help keep internal and external stakeholders well informed about the project, its long-term impact, and raise awareness and recognition amongst the wider community.

Download the [communication toolkit for ARDC co-investment projects](#).

Australian Research Data Commons

Acknowledging the Use of ARDC Services and Co-Invested Outputs and Services

For guidelines on how to acknowledge the use of ARDC services and co-invested outputs and services, visit <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17096414>.